

DEI - A Review of Initiatives and Accountability Frameworks

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INTRODUCTION

Organizations all over the world are defining their work cultures in large part via diversity and inclusion. Organizations are constantly searching for comprehensive approaches to advance their diversity and inclusion journey and foster a meaningful sense of belonging for their workforce. Diversity, equity and inclusion policies are only as good as the people responsible for carrying them out. The entire burden cannot fall on human resource manager because talent management is simply one component of diversity, equity and inclusion's business strategy. Corporate leaders must demonstrate that they are genuine leaders with a vision for diversity and equity as well as a proven track record in sales and growth. Having diversity and inclusion will improve the balance of opinions, views in any setting. A well-balanced world will accept different opinions and reduce fears towards differences. A well-balanced world can also improve the average cultural competency in the society. People like to fit in, so they are cautious about sticking their necks out. When corporates have a strong, homogenous culture, they stifle the natural cognitive diversity in groups through the pressure to conform.

An effective and well-conducted review as a research method creates a firm foundation for advancing knowledge and facilitating theory development (Webster & Watson, 2002). By integrating findings and perspectives from many empirical findings, a literature review can address research questions with a power that no single study has. This qualitative exploratory research applies probes through research articles online/offline, books, reports and other published texts.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The benefits that diversity, equity and inclusion strategies reap are women in the workplace stay with gender equality leaders, if employees trust their employer's commitments, their engagement level can increase up to 20%, and the likelihood they will leave their organization decreases by 87%. Companies report 19% higher revenue than traditional organization, 25% greater likelihood of being more profitable in the marketplace, 75% of companies with strong diversity, equity inclusion will surpass their financial goals. Employees of such organization with strong diversity equity and inclusion strategy are 9.8 times more likely to look forward to work. Such employees are also 6.3 times more likely to take pride in their job

According to Mckinsey insights: Companies in the top quartile for both gender and ethnic diversity are 12 percent more likely to outperform all other companies in the data set. Executives team in an organization where in there is more than 30% women are more likely to outperform those with fewer or no women in their teams. The research also shows that a diverse company has 2.3 times higher cash flow per employee, and that inclusive teams improve performance by up to 30%.

The diversity equity and inclusion strategies are not only important to attract potential talent in the organization but the initiatives are also important for consumers in the market.

According to the research the consumers are making decision based on company values, 48% of the consumers want companies to focus on social issues like diversity, equity and inclusion. 76% of the consumers will discontinue their relationships with companies who treat the environment, community or the employees in which they operate, poorly. Gender diversity will bring in investment and innovation from different gender; cultural diversity will bring in ideas and traditional wisdom from other cultures; age diversity will bring in experience and problem-solving methods from people with different historical experiences. All these ideas will bring attract different investment because people in a diverse environment understand the needs better

ABSTRACT

This research paper reviews the diversity, equity and inclusion initiatives undertaken by well-known corporates in various sectors. The paper also discusses various quantitative and qualitative frameworks for driving better accountability around diversity, equity and inclusion initiatives. The paper takes into account different sectors and the key players in these sectors to understand the best practices that the organizations adopt to drive the diversity equity and inclusion strategies. These sectors include consulting, hospitality, media industry, manufacturing industry and banking financial services and insurance (BFSI) sector. The consulting sector further includes Kantar, India (BCG). The hospitality sector includes AirAsia India Limited, Thomas Cook (India) Limited. The media industry includes Zee Entertainment Enterprise Limited and Bennett Coleman and Co Ltd, Times Group. The manufacturing sector includes MG Motor India and Alfa Laval. The banking financial services and insurance (BFSI) sector includes MAX life insurance and Aditya Birla Capital

The paper also provides key insights to the benefits of having a holistic diversity equity and inclusion strategy in place. The research paper provides in-depth understanding of the key metrics used by different organization to measure the success of their diversity, equity and inclusion initiatives. These metrics include diversity equity and inclusion workshop participation goals, completion rate of workshops, number of mentorship programs and hours spent on mentorship, number of incident reports, the number of employees participating in affinity groups or employee resource groups (ERGs), the percentage of leaders sponsoring a resource group, leadership attendance at diversity equity and inclusion initiatives.

OBJECTIVES

The paper helps the diversity and inclusion officers/managers with different rules that could be applied by them in order to increase diversity in their organization. The qualitative frameworks to drive the diversity, equity and inclusion goals include anonymous hotline number to report misconduct and bad behavior, diversity equity and inclusion accountability with meaningful rewards understand what pronouns are preferred by the employees in the organization, promote transparency, ask about diversity equity and

inclusion in exit interviews, annual engagement survey, pulse survey.

Keywords:

Diversity, equity, inclusion, media, consulting, hospitality, manufacturing, banking financial services and insurance (BFSI)

LITERATURE REVIEW

DEI was “Tick in the box” – all many years as a subject. This means something we speak so highly about in public forums but couldn’t care less when it comes to implementation. But today Diversity and Inclusion are playing a big role in defining work culture for organizations across the globe. Organizations are always looking out for comprehensive ways to further their D&I journey and create true belonging for their employees. While some organizations have just begun their D&I journey, some organizations have been working on diversity and inclusion proactively for years. It is safe to say that while some organizations will be good with certain practices, other organizations are effective with certain other practices. Surveys were conducted so that organizations get to learn from each other and pick up key initiatives with a proven success record. These surveys also gave insights as to what are perceptions of people regarding the DEI initiatives in the organizations. It was found that most organizations. A common theme emerging from various workplace diversity studies is that people tend to gravitate toward others that look, act and think like themselves. This is a form of unconscious bias that can lead to a homogenous working environment — encouraging “groupthink” and deterring individuals with differing opinions or ideas from speaking up. A workplace culture like this can mean lack of innovation and low employee morale. To achieve true cognitive diversity in the workplace, it has to be authentically integrated into all aspects of company culture. Employees should feel free and safe to share ideas, criticisms and suggestions for alternate routes. In practice, this means providing meeting spaces or open forums where employees feel comfortable speaking up and are encouraged to think outside the norm. Consider hiring job candidates that are a culture add, instead of a culture fit. This means looking for talent that brings in a fresh perspective, instead of people who share similar ideas as the employees already on the team

STRATEGIES USED BY DIFFERENT ORGANIZATIONS

MAX life insurance (BFSI)

- **Diversity Toolkit** - a toolkit designed for People Managers for awareness, sensitization amongst employees
- **Catalyst**: Is a signature program that is internally curated for mid-level women to enable them build their own brand and aspire them to take larger/next and stretched roles.
- **Roar Ahead**: - Another signature capability development program; ROAR was conceptualized for senior women leaders.

Aditya Birla Capital (BFSI)

- **ABC Career Restart session**: Was held for women family members and friend of employee.
- Women employee's additional benefits like **Flexi Work**, Returnity and career management support.
- **The Travel policy** provides care giver and child travel and additional entitlement on accommodation.
- **ABC Her Café** - this is an employee resource group for Women employees at ABC.
- **TARA program**: Focuses on building and strengthening leadership capability in our women employees.
- **WoMentoring** - Building mentoring capability in our women leaders in mid-management
- **Connect Conversations**: One-on-One conversation with the women talent pool to understand their work experience.

Alfa Laval (Manufacturing)

- **The Speed Coaching program**: Supports both men and women with career and personal guidance under various topics such as Breaking the Barriers, Work-Life Balance, and Effective Networking.
- **The self-introspection**: Under self-introspection sessions, the aim is

to understand and grasp how our colleagues perceive us which increase our awareness levels by helping us understand our blind spots.

- **Retain** - The wellness sessions address physical, financial, mental health, and well-being. Recently we did our financial wellness sessions

MG Motor India (Manufacturing)

- **Gender Censors Profile Sharing:** Further reducing the unconscious bias in hiring managers.
- The MG team works closely with the local **panchayats** near its factory in Halol, Gujarat, to reach out to nearby villages.
- **NEEM Program:** enabling skill training in women from rural areas at the plant
- **Drive Her Back program.** Launched in 2019, it allows qualified and experienced women to return to their workplace with pride and dignity,
- **Women Interactive Network for Development (WIND),** a structured network to meet and discuss learning opportunities for self-development.
- **Crèche facility:** At the plant and head office to help new mothers manage their work and family and also provide with 'Parenthood' kits.

Zee Entertainment Enterprise Ltd (Media)

- **Focused group discussions:** Held with senior women leaders to find out the support they need
- **Extra days of paid leaves,** ergonomics furniture as well as preferential parking lots
- **Posh awareness modules** by way of e-learning
- **Think and Do tank** and called it the DEI Cell. It comprises of self-nominated employees from diverse backgrounds (research, sales, marketing, content) working towards achieving the DEI goal at Zee
- **Creation of a monthly newsletter** - This acts as a wrap up document for all that has happened on DEI and shared monthly, sharing pieces of information called inclusion nudges every week
- **Blind talent assessment instruments:** Recruiter and Hiring Manager

sensitization workshops on screening candidates through gender blind talent assessment instruments

- **Second career program:** Along with programs for women leadership development

Bennett Coleman and Co Ltd, Times Group (Media)

- **Club of XtraOrdinary Women:** Is a platform to connect like-minded professional women to create, inspire each other.
- **Home drop and Guesthouse facility.**
- **Times She UnLTD. Entrepreneur Awards.,**
- **Times Women Drive** is the largest & most celebrated all women's car rally.
- **Out & Proud campaign:** Portrays a captivating story of people from the LGBTQ community and their families
- **Sindoor Khela:** Traditionally only married women would celebrate Sindoor Khela but in new sindoor khela campaign, an inclusive celebration where all women – be itsingle, divorcee, widow, transgender, sex worker or any woman can participate

AirAsia India Limited (Hospitality)

- **Default rating of 3 (performance grade - good):** For women in security department who were pregnant in the year 2020-21
- **Six focus group discussions:** In order to understand how safe our women allstars felt at work, he questions and discussions centred on how to make AAI safe for women and to understand their concerns and to implement the same
- **Safety Manual in Braille:** In-flight Safety manual in Braille - In Dec 2021, AirAsia India announced the introduction of a new in-flight safety manual in braille.
- **Disability Equality Training:** All allstars who work at the airport are mandatorily trained required by the DGCA

The Boston Consulting Group India (Consulting):

- **Back to Home' program:** For women alumni
- **2nd innings program:** For those who have taken a break in their careers.
- **One program:** Ensures that every woman and every Pride member in the system has a mentor they can reach out to for help, support, and guidance at a professional as well as personal level.
- **Caregiver leave / Leave of Absence:** Where an employee can take a break to focus on yourself or loved ones
- **Buddy programme:** For women and LGBTQ applicants (fully confidential), through which we map an applicant to a buddy who identifies as a part of the respective community and can support the applicant through the screening process while addressing queries related to our culture, policies
- **Coffee catch-ups:** Cohort connects, and breakout discussions to enable all women and Pride members to easily access mentors and support groups (across genders).
- **Gender-neutral washrooms** as well as wheelchair accessibility.
- **Celebrating our Values program:** Ensures that every employee has a forum to connect and talk about what is important to them
- **Gender-neutral language and inclusive icons**
- **Partnership with the government and not-for-profit bodies:** To ensure the better inclusion of under-represented communities in policies and benefits
- **ME days:** Additional holidays on which the firm remains closed.
- **Flex-time:** Where employees can work for fewer hours a day
- **Flex days:** Where employees can work for fewer days in the week

Kantar (Consulting)

- **Partnerships with consultant and recruitment organizations**
- **3+1 Approach:** Three consistent themes which are globally aligned and one additional priority for the local context

ANALYSIS

Questions	No	Don't know	Yes
Do you have documented zero tolerance policy against violence at work?	22%	5%	73%
Does your company have a POSH committee	2%	5%	93%
Is cognitive diversity one of the criteria of your company's HR policy while hiring professionals?	27%	17%	56%
In the last 3 years, did women constitute at least 33% of your overall hires?	44%	12%	44%
Is there any pay gap between women and men for same roles at any level of management – are women being paid less?	83%	12%	5%
Do minority communities constitute at least 20% of your workforce?	32%	58%	10%
Increase in percentage of professionals with disabilities in total workforce over last 3 years	59%	19%	22%
In the last three years, did your company hire at least 5% of total hires above 50yrs of age?	58%	20%	22%

Table 1.1

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Can't say	Agree	Strongly Agree
LGBTQ+ community is welcomed, and its sensitivities are respected in the company	-	5%	41%	22%	32%
Are there policies to promote inclusion of religion, caste, class, race and background at your workplace?	2%	12	24%	22%	40%
Company promotes equal remuneration, including benefits, for work of equal value to men and women	-	-	-	27%	73%
Company does not discriminate while hiring or promoting employees based on age	-	5%	7%	32%	56%
Company has ensured women feel safe while working and has taken strong measures to prevent sexual harassment	-	-	5%	10%	85%
Company strives to offer flexible work options	-	-	3%	51%	44%

Table 1.2

The analysis shows that even after making use of the best resources and coming up with best initiatives is not enough. We can see in the above table that the ground reality is different. Table 1.1 shows that huge percentage of employees have answered “no” this shows that ground reality is different Even though the organization put their best foot forward for their DEI initiatives it

was observed that in most cases a significant chunk of employees of the organization didn't know about the policies, initiatives for DEI. It is this part of the workforce that needs to be sensitized and made aware of the initiatives to create diverse, equitable, inclusive workforce.

DISCUSSION

Today the discussion has moved from DEI to DEIB which is diversity, equity, inclusion, and belonging. Diversity, equity, inclusion and belonging (DEIB) is an initiative geared towards eliminating discrimination, bias and harassment and creating a diverse and inclusive workplace that promotes innovation and growth. In order to create diverse, equitable and inclusive workplace, organization are now adopting Artificial Intelligence more than ever AI is not 'intelligent' in the real sense, but just an efficient way of categorizing data. More specifically, it is built to analyze patterns in data AI-based chatbots like Mya help to know if candidates with lighter skin tones are more favored. In fact, AI is helping to identify biases even in past hiring decisions

IMPLICATIONS

DEI initiatives require constant efforts, sensitization, training so as to create inclusive organization. The senior leaders should model DEI behaviors in all of their interactions and communications. The leaders need to walk the talk, they need to continuously reinforce the DEI principles and practices. Communication plays a vital role while rolling out DEI initiatives The DEI metrics that an organization measures and manages should align with their program's strategic objectives. Some companies may emphasize key performance indicators (KPIs) related to gender diversity in leadership roles, while others prioritize KPIs related to racial diversity throughout the workforce. Organizations should identify three to five DEI KPIs that help them monitor and continually improve the program's performance. Tracking one or two metrics may not provide a sufficiently comprehensive assessment of performance; tracking too many KPIs raises questions about the program's priorities. Financial investments are not the foundation of success of DEI initiative in organization. Although organizations require sufficient money for DEI initiatives. The success will depend upon behaviors of leaders, communication and the benefits that employees can reap from being diverse, inclusive.

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